

Investigation of the Effect of Architectural Design Patterns on Software Quality in Mobile Platforms

Furkan ÖZBAY^{1,*}, Oya KALIPSIZ²

^{1,2} *Yıldız Technical University, Faculty of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, İstanbul, Turkey*

Abstract

With the increase in the capabilities of mobile platforms in recent years, the importance and cost of mobile platforms have increased. Mobile platforms and applications undergo many changes during the process they serve, both in terms of user requirements and bug fixes. The software code must be of high quality so that the software can adapt quickly to the changes that are desired to be made. According to studies, software that lacks software quality can have a devastating effect on both companies and national economies. Low-quality software can also have moral damages such as loss of reputation, apart from material damages. A company's release of low-quality software and victimization of users reduces both customers' and investors' trust in the company. Since the quality of the software is so important and its increasing importance, the fact that the software prepared is above a certain quality, the importance given to finding and solving the errors during the development of the project has naturally increased. To provide this it is important to review development factors and improve the development process. One of the important factors of development is deciding on the design of the software. Architectural design patterns have an important role to shape software design in numerous ways. Another important factor in the development process is measuring code quality. Measuring metrics and tools are needed to analyze the code quality of software scientifically. Studies on the relationship between these metrics and software quality, their importance, and the less costly and consistent measurement of software quality have been revealed.

In this study, under the development requirements heading, the effects of using different architectural design patterns on a sample Android application project, namely a To-do application, was written in both architectural design patterns, namely MVP and MVVM was investigated, and answers were sought for the question of does architectural design patterns differ. As a result, it has been proven that different architectural design patterns have different effects on Android projects.

Keywords: Software quality, code quality, architectural design patterns.

* Corresponded Author

INTRODUCTION

The importance of mobile platforms and their applications is growing as a result of the advancement of mobile technologies. As a result, the software community exerts a great deal of effort to ensure that the software is of high quality, low in costs, and easy to maintain. According to [1], the total cost of low-quality software to the United States economy is approximately \$2.08 trillion in 2020. According to the same study, \$1.6 trillion was spent on information systems in the United States in 2020, with approximately 75% of this, or \$1.2 trillion, spent on the maintenance of old systems. Two-thirds of this amount was accepted as waste, resulting in a waste of approximately 800 billion dollars. In addition to economic damages, low-quality software can cause moral harm such as loss of reputation. Customers' and investors' trust in a company is eroded when it releases low-quality software and victimizes users. Because the quality of the software is so important and its increasing importance, the fact that the software prepared is above a certain quality, the importance given to finding and correcting errors during project development has naturally increased. While fulfilling responsibilities that change and grow daily, the software must also meet requirements such as speed, low cost, security, stability, and error-free operation. If the software fails to meet such requirements, the development process may take longer, incurring costs such as developer fees as well as project cancellation. Also, the maintenance phase, which begins after the development process is completed, may result in issues such as time loss and cost burden for both the developer and the employer. Another critical point is software errors; as a result of these errors, significant losses may occur. To prevent such undesirable situations, the development phase of software is very important. The purpose of the software development phase is to increase the quality of the software and thus produce a higher quality software product.

In [2], Lou stated that software quality can be reviewed under two headings: development requirements such as understandability and modifiability, secondly operational requirements such as usability and performance. Software is quality software to the extent that it can meet both development and operational requirements. Because software that is high in code quality may have low availability.

In ISO 9126 standard [3], software quality metrics are defined. The software quality metrics are needed to make comparisons and get insights into the software from viewpoint of the engineer [4]. A study on subjects such as the relationship between these metrics and software quality, their importance, and measuring the quality of software in a less costly and consistent way has been revealed [5].

Software quality models [6] are created to identify the factors that affect the quality and create a set of metrics that measure these factors, thus collecting data that will help evaluate the quality of

the software. An example of software quality models is the ISO/IEC 9126-1 [7] quality model. This software quality model is an international standard and is based on McCall's (1977) and Boehm's (1978) models [8].

In this study, the popular architectural design patterns in the Android mobile platform are examined in terms of software code quality. These design patterns and the results are given by using software quality metrics for the differences between two different architectural design patterns of the same application.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A program's or computing system's software architecture is the system's structure or structures, which include software elements, their externally visible properties, and their relationships [9]. Design patterns ensure that previously proven designs that meet specific needs can be reused. These proven techniques, used and adopted by the developer community, become reusable thanks to design patterns. Thus, both the burden of the developers is reduced, and the developers avoid the problems and costs that may arise as a result of incorrect architectural setup. Wrong or non-optimal writing of software; it can cause bugs to be found during the development phase of the software or later, prolonging the writing of the source code and thus prolonging the project, thus increasing the time cost, reducing the maintainability of the source code, and finally reducing the understandability. In particular, the decrease in intelligibility has a great negative impact on the project. Today, many design patterns are actively used or not. As with many other platforms, architectural design patterns such as MVC (Model-View-Controller), MVP (Model-View-Presenter), MVVM (Model-View-ViewModel), MVI (Model-View-Intent), and VIPER (View-Interactor-Presenter-Entity-Router) are commonly used on mobile platforms. There are many studies and comparisons on these architectural design patterns such as [2, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18]. In [19], the study examines the software quality and maintainability of design patterns in object-oriented software and the results which were obtained by applying different design patterns to existing software are examined. The design patterns for the IOS platform are examined under the title of software quality in [20] to develop quality code and reduce the cost on mobile platforms and made suggestions for cost reduction and finally added a new software design pattern to the literature.

Software Quality Metrics

To analyze and calculate the software code quality, there should be metrics that calculations depend on. There are numerous code quality metrics in the literature but in this study, some of the most known quality metrics and attributes are considered. To elaborate, dividing those into four

categories as project level, package level, class level and method level as in [21] might be helpful but the categorization might differ from person to person.

1. Project-Level Software Quality Metrics

There are numerous metrics available to assess and demonstrate project-level software quality. These metrics indicate the software's overall quality impressions.

1.1. MOOD Metrics Set

MOOD metrics [22] are designed to express the general quality of object-oriented projects. It defines a set of six quality factors as follows: MHF (Method Hiding Factor), AHF (Attribute Hiding Factor), MIF (Method Inheritance Factor), AIF (Attribute Inheritance Factor), PF (Polymorphism Factor), and CF (Coupling Factor)

1.2. QMOOD Metrics and Quality Attributes Set

Quality Model for Object-Oriented Design (QMOOD) [23] is a comprehensive quality model that establishes well defined and validated model to assess object-oriented design quality attributes such as extendibility and flexibility and express it through object-oriented design properties such as encapsulation and coupling. To obtain those properties, a list of metrics such as design class size metric and number of methods metrics are used.

2. Package-Level Software Quality Metrics

It is a set of quality measures used to represent the overall software package's quality. Packages are a collection of related concrete or abstract classes, interfaces, sub-packages, and other items. The following is a list of Robert C. Martin's most well-known package-level metrics [24, 25]: I (Instability), A (Abstractness), D (Efferent Coupling), Ce (Efferent Coupling), Ca (Afferent Coupling), Ce (Efferent Coupling), Ca (Afferent Coupling), Ce (Efferent Coupling), Ca (Afferent Co (Normalized distance from the main sequence)

3. Class-Level Software Quality Metrics

There are numerous metrics available for measuring and illustrating class-level software quality. The Chidamber-Kemerer metrics [26] are the most well-known. As an abbreviation, it is known as CK metrics. Other metrics include the Lorenz-Kidd metrics [27], the Li-Henry metrics [28], the Lanza-Marinescu metrics [29], and the Bieman-Kang metrics [30].

3.1. Chidamber-Kemerer Metrics

It is a set of metrics for object-oriented systems introduced by Chidamber and Kemerer in 1994. Metrics are characterized as six items as follows: WMC (Weighted Methods per Class), DIT

(Depth of Inheritance Tree), NOC (Number of Children), CBO (Coupling Between Object Classes), RFC (Response for a Class), and LCOM (Lack of Cohesion in Methods)

3.2. Lorenz-Kidd Metrics

Lorenz and Kidd proposed a set of metrics that can be grouped as internal, external, size, and inheritance. The main metrics are as follows: NOA (Number of Attributes), NOO (Number of Operations), NOAM (Number of Added Methods), and NOOM (Number of Overridden Methods)

3.3. Li-Henry Metrics

In 1993, Li and Henry proposed a set of metrics and observed the maintenance effort of two systems with their metrics. At the end of the observation, they defined the metrics that can be listed as follows: SIZE1 (Number of Procedures or Functions), SIZE2 (Number of Attributes and Methods), MPC (Message Passing Coupling), DAC (Data Abstraction Coupling), NOM (Number of Methods)

3.4. Lanza-Marinescu Metrics

In the [29], Lanza and Marinescu analyzed design flaws and called them disharmonies. They defined eleven flaws and suggested a metrics-based model for those. Some of the metrics of that model are as follows; ATFD (Access to Foreign Data), NOAV (Number of Accessed Variables), NOPA (Number of Public Attributes), NOAM (Number of Accessor Methods), CDISP (Coupling Dispersion), and WOC (Weight of a Class)

3.5. Bieman-Kang Metrics

In 1995, Bieman and Kang defined two metrics of class cohesion based on the direct and indirect connections of method pairs [30]. They are as follows; TCC (Tight Class Cohesion) and LCC (Loose Class Cohesion)

4. Method-Level Software Quality Metrics

These metrics measure method-specific quality and show the overall quality. Some of the method-level quality metrics can be listed as follows: LOC (Lines of Code), CC (McCabe Cyclomatic Complexity), maximum nesting depth, loop nesting depth, condition nesting depth, number of loops, LAA (Locality of Attribute Accesses), FDP (Foreign Data Providers), NOAV (Number of Accessed Variables), CINT (Coupling Intensity), CDISP (Coupling Dispersion)

METHODOLOGY

In recent years, mobile platform apps have gained more attention. Day after day, more companies invest in the mobile side since plenty of users have gained the habit of doing many things on their

smartphones. As expected, companies expect any risk or cost to be at a minimum level. There are many ways to keep costs and risks at a low level for software projects such as: reducing development time, reducing maintenance work, minimizing errors, and increasing reliability and security. Such processes have a great impact in the terms of cost and risk. At this point, keeping the code quality high and selecting suitable software architecture patterns are crucial tasks for software projects.

The metrics mentioned earlier were calculated for the Android sample project written with two different architectural software patterns named MVP (Model-View-Presenter) and MVVM (Model-View-ViewModel). The results were observed and the “Do different architectural patterns have effects on software quality?” question was tried to be answered.

1. Project Selection

A sample project written in both different architectural patterns was searched over Github [31]. After eliminating some candidate projects, a to-do project [32] was selected. This project is created as guidance of architectural patterns on the Android platform for Android application developers by Google. Although there are multiple versions of this project, only the MVP and MVVM versions were taken into consideration in this study.

2. Environment Selection

To quickly read, analyze, and run software codes, an integrated development environment (IDE) is required. On the Android platform, the most well-known are Eclipse [33] and Android Studio [34]. Android Studio was chosen for this study because of its popularity, ease of use, and capabilities [35].

Android framework has abandoned the Eclipse Integrated Development Environment (IDE) with Android Development Tools (ADT) in favor of IntelliJ IDEA in 64-bit Android 5.0 and later. (Integrated Development Environment Application) [36].

3. Metrics and Metric Tools Selection

This study considers and employs nearly all metrics given in the quality metrics section. The following metrics tools were used in the study: MetricsTree [37] is an IDE addon for evaluating the quantitative features of Java code. At the project, package, class, and method levels, it measures the most common sets of metrics [21]. It is one of the tools used to assess the software quality metrics mentioned earlier. MetricsReloaded [38] is also an IDE addon that aids in the evaluation of quality metrics like MetricsTree. Finally, another measuring tool employed in this study was JaSoMe (Java Source Metrics) [39]. The purpose of using different tools to perform almost identical computations is to validate by comparing metric results. Because practically

every tool contains faults or miscalculates some metrics, customized computations of some metrics by modifying formulas, and includes or excludes test resources. As a result, verifying the results from tools is important.

4. Metrics Calculation

With the three tools mentioned in the previous section, both versions of the project were investigated in terms of project-level, package-level, class-level, and method-level metrics. Calculating metrics on these tools is simple and does not require any additional configuration, files, or programs.

First, project-level metrics were examined. The three metric tools were run by selecting the versions' root folders. The metrics results were examined and recorded. Different tool result metrics were compared, and the reasons for the differences were investigated.

In the following step, package-level metrics were examined. Different packages were investigated separately using three tools. Packages with the most metric differences were sought out and noted for future comparisons. Class-level metrics were examined as a third step. Visual and business-related classes were prioritized over test and utility classes. Classes that have the most metrics differences and have the same logic for the app tried to be found and results are noted.

As a fourth step, method-level metrics were analyzed. As in the third step, visual and business-related classes were prioritized. Methods that have most metrics differences and the same logic in both versions were tried to be found and results are noted.

5. Results Comparison

All metrics results from both MVP and MVVM project versions are analyzed using three software quality metrics tools. Initially, results from the same tools are compared for both versions of the application. Later, each metric from different tools was compared and analyzed to lead to a conclusion. The detailed explanations of each level metric results and sample results for the given level from MetricsTree [37] are given.

5.1 Project-Level Metrics Comparison

In terms of project-level metrics, one could tell the inheritance paradigm of object-oriented design shows itself in the MVP version more than in the MVVM version just by considering the better extendibility and reusability metrics result in **Table 1**. At first, it may seem a good idea but looking at understandability metrics decreases, it shows that the complexity of design is increased. Hence, possibly maintainability costs are also increased since maintainability requires understandability in the first place.

Table 1. Results of sample project-level metrics

Quality Metric/Attribute	Metrics/Attributes Set	Result for MVP	Result for MVVM
Attribute Hiding Factor	MOOD	90,61%	85,06%
Coupling Factor	MOOD	4,43%	4,11%
Extendibility	QMOOD	1,09	0,89
Reusability	QMOOD	2,24	1,63
Understandability	QMOOD	-3,81	-3,52

5.2 Package-Level Metrics Comparison

In terms of package-level metrics, all packages in both versions are analyzed. As an example, the “taskdetail” package results for both versions are given in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Results of package-level metrics for the “taskdetail” package

Quality Metric	Metrics Set	Result for MVP	Result for MVVM
Abstractness	Robert C. Martin	0,5	0,4
Afferent Coupling	Robert C. Martin	1	3
Efferent Coupling	Robert C. Martin	9	8
Instability	Robert C. Martin	0,9	0,72
Normalized Distance from Main Sequence	Robert C. Martin	0,4	0,12

As seen in **Table 2**, the abstractness value is higher in the MVP version due to the usage of the contract interfaces. Also, considering afferent and efferent coupling, in the MVVM version, classes in the mentioned package are used in other packages more than in the MVP version. It also indicates better component stability but less portability and modifiability as also in shown instability metric value.

5.3 Class-Level Metrics Comparison

In terms of class-level metrics, all classes in both versions that are similar in terms of what they are doing, are analyzed. As an example, a few metrics results for the “TaskDetailFragment” class of both versions are given in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Results of class-level metrics for the “TaskDetailFragment” class

Quality Metric	Metrics Set	Result for MVP	Result for MVVM
Weighted Methods per Class	Chidamber-Kemerer	24	11
Response for a Class	Chidamber-Kemerer	48	32
Number of Operations	Lorenz-Kidd	216	193
Number of Attributes and Methods	Li-Henry	267	241

As seen in **Table 3**, the metrics of the MVP version are higher than the MVVM version. This shows that the comments in the project-level comparison apply here too. Having mentioned metrics in higher value possibly leads to decrease class understandability and higher maintenance costs.

5.4 Method-Level Metrics Comparison

In terms of method-level metrics, lots of methods in both versions that are similar in terms of what they are doing are analyzed. As an example, a few metrics results for the “loadStatistics” method are given in **Table 4**.

Table 4. Results of method-level metrics for the “loadStatistics” method

Quality Metric	Metrics Set	Result for MVP	Result for MVVM
LOC	-	41	17
Cyclomatic Complexity	McCabe	6	1
Maximum Nesting Depth	Lanza-Marinescu	4	2

As seen in **Table 4**, the results are in favor of the MVVM version. This also shows that the comments in the project-level comparison apply here too. Having mentioned metrics in higher numeric values possibly leads to decrease method understandability and higher maintenance costs.

CONCLUSION

In software projects, by choosing a suitable architectural pattern, numerous software quality metrics can be kept at the desired level. Thus, exerting those metrics and obtaining results helps to analyze the situation of the project in terms of quality, and modification of the software code can be done.

In this study, some of the most known software quality metrics were used to calculate the effect of different design patterns on software quality. This study shows that an architectural design pattern may have different effects on different metrics. For example, it may increase the extendibility metric while decreasing the understandability metric. In conclusion, an architectural design pattern is an important component of software and should always be selected according to the project's current and future needs. Otherwise, it may lead the poor design and poor software quality.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Krasner, "The Cost of Poor Software Quality in the US: A 2020 Report, 2020," Consortium for IT Software Quality (CISQ), Jan. 1, 2021. Accessed: Apr. 25, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.it-cisq.org/pdf/CPSQ-2020-report.pdf>
- [2] T. Lou, "A comparison of Android native app architecture MVC, MVP and MVVM," M.S. thesis, Eindhoven University of Technology, 2016.
- [3] ISO, *Software Product Evaluation - Quality Characteristics and Guidelines for their Use*. ISO/IEC IS 9126, Geneva, Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization, 1991.
- [4] U. Erdemir, U. Tekin, F. Buzluca, "Nesneye dayalı yazılım metrikleri ve yazılım kalitesi," *Yazılım Kalitesi ve Yazılım Gelistirme Araçları Sempozyumu*, 2008.
- [5] E. B. Belachew, "Analysis of software quality using software metrics," *International Journal on Computational Science & Applications*, vol. 8, no. 4/5, pp. 11-20, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.5121/ijcsa.2018.8502.
- [6] ISO, *ISO Standard 8402: Quality management and quality assurance - Vocabulary*, ISO/TC 8402, Geneva, Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization, 1994.
- [7] ISO, *Software Engineering - Product Quality - Part 1: Quality Model*. ISO/IEC 9126-1, Geneva, Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization, 2001.
- [8] "ISO 9126 Software Quality Characteristics," sqa.net. <http://www.sqa.net/iso9126.html> (accessed: Apr. 25, 2022).
- [9] L. Bass, P. Clements and R. Kazman, *Software Architecture in Practice*, 2nd ed. Addison-Wesley Professional, 2003, pp. 23.
- [10] G. Kresner and S. Pope, "A Description of the Model-View-Controller User Interface Paradigm in the Smalltalk-80 System," *Journal of Object-oriented Programming*, vol. 1, 1988.
- [11] Y. Zhang and Y. Luo, "An architecture and implement model for Model-View-Presenter pattern," *3rd International Conference on Computer Science and Information Technology*, vol. 8, Jul. 2010, pp. 532-536, doi: 10.1109/ICCSIT.2010.5565090.
- [12] J. Kouraklis, *MVVM in Delphi*, Apress, 2016, pp. 1-12.
- [13] N. Akhtar and S. Ghafoor, "Analysis of Architectural Patterns for Android Development," Fatima Jinnah Women University, 2021. Accessed: Apr. 27, 2022. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352021976_Analysis_of_Architectural_Patterns_for_Android_Development
- [14] K. Chauhan, S. Kumar, D. Sethia and M. N. Alam, "Performance Analysis of Kotlin Coroutines on Android in a Model-View-Intent Architecture pattern," *2nd International Conference for Emerging Technology (INCET)*, 2021, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/INCET51464.2021.9456197.

- [15] D. Dobrean and L. Dioşan, "A comparative study of software architectures in mobile applications," *Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai, Informatica*, vol. 64, no. 2, pp. 49-64, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.24193/subbi.2019.2.
- [16] V. Humeniuk, "Android Architecture Comparison: MVP vs. VIPER," M.S. thesis, Linnaeus University, 2019.
- [17] Y. Haravy and S. Surto, "Modern Approaches to Android APP Architecture: MVVM, MVP, VIPER," *Европейский и национальный контексты в научных исследованиях: electronic collected materials of X Junior Researcher' Conference*, vol. 8, May 2018, pp. 206-208.
- [18] B. Wisnuadhi, G. Munawar and U. Wahyu, "Performance Comparison of Native Android Application on MVP and MVVM", *Proceedings of the International Seminar of Science and Applied Technology (ISSAT 2020)*, 2020. Accessed: May. 2, 2022, doi: 10.2991/aer.k.201221.047
- [19] T. Türk, "The Effect of Software Design Patterns on Object-Oriented Software Quality and Maintainability," M.S. thesis, Middle East Technical University, 2009.
- [20] N. G. Alp, "Mobil platformlarda kaliteli kod geliştirilmesi ve maliyetin azaltılması," M.S thesis, Beykent University, 2019.
- [21] "MetricsTree IntelliJ IDEA plugin," github.com. <https://www.github.com/b333vv/metricstree#readme> (accessed May. 17, 2022).
- [22] F. B. Abreu and R. Carapuça, "Object-oriented software engineering: Measuring and controlling the development process", *Proceedings of the 4th international conference on software quality*, vol. 186, 1994.
- [23] J. Bansiya and C. G. Davis, "A hierarchical model for object-oriented design quality assessment," *IEEE Transactions on software engineering*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 4-17, Jan. 2002, doi: 10.1109/32.979986.
- [24] R. Martin, "OO design quality metrics: an analysis of dependencies," *Workshop on Pragmatic and Theoretical Directions in Object Oriented Software Metrics at OOPSLA*, 1994.
- [25] M. Lorenz and J. Kidd, *Object-oriented software metrics: a practical guide*, Prentice-Hall, 1994.
- [26] S. R. Chidamber and C. F. Kemerer, "A metrics suite for object oriented design," *IEEE Transactions on software engineering*, vol. 20, no. 6, pp. 476-493, 1994.
- [27] M. Lorenz and J. Kidd, *Object Oriented Software Metrics*, Prentice-Hall, Inc., 1994.
- [28] W. Li and S. Henry, "Object-oriented metrics that predict maintainability," *Journal of systems and software*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 111-122, 1993.
- [29] M. Lanza and R. Marinescu, *Object-Oriented Metrics in Practice*, 1st ed. Springer-Verlag, 2006, pp. 23.

- [30] J. Biman and B. Kang, "Cohesion and reuse in an object-oriented system," *ACM SIGSOFT Software Engineering Notes*, vol. 20, pp. 259-262, 1995.
- [31] "Github," github.com. <https://www.github.com> (accessed May. 12, 2022).
- [32] "Android Architecture Blueprints," github.com. <https://www.github.com/android/architecture-samples> (accessed: May. 17, 2022).
- [33] "Enabling Open Innovation & Collaboration | The Eclipse Foundation," eclipse.org. <https://www.eclipse.org> (accessed May. 17, 2022).
- [34] "Android Studio," android.com. <https://developer.android.com/studio> (accessed May. 20, 2022).
- [35] "Android Studio Vs Eclipse - Which is Better for Android Developers?," data-flair.training. <https://www.data-flair.training/blogs/android-studio-vs-eclipse> (accessed: May. 20, 2022).
- [36] J. Wallace, "An Introduction to Android 7.0 Nougat," in *Android Apps for Absolute Beginners: Covering Android 7*, Apress, 2017, pp. 1-15.
- [37] "MetricsTree," plugins.jetbrains.com. <https://plugins.jetbrains.com/plugin/13959-metricstree> (accessed May. 23, 2022).
- [38] "MetricsReloaded," plugins.jetbrains.com. <https://plugins.jetbrains.com/plugin/93-metricsreloaded> (accessed May. 23, 2022).
- [39] "JaSoMe: Java Source Metrics," github.com. <https://github.com/rodhilton/jasome> (accessed May. 23, 2022).